

Milestone 9: Documented connection established with the key national funding agencies, ministries and RPOs in Europe

Work package n°	3
Milestone / Deliverable n°	MS9 / MS3.1
Lead beneficiary	UHEL
Document Type	Internal Report
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	31 January 2022 (M10)
Actual delivery date	23 September 2022 (M18)
Version	01
Reviewed by	
Accepted by	
Comments	

Authors: Tuukka Petäjä, Silja Häme, Paolo Laj, Ulla Wandinger, Jochen Wagner, Carmela Cornacchia, Rosa Petrarca, Arnoud Apituley, Iwona Stachlewska, Milan Vana, Jakub Ondracek, Hanna K. Lappalainen, Lucas Alados Arboledas, Jean Francois Doussin, Eija Juurola

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Table of Content

Introduction

3

National Consortia and respective National Contact Points

3

Connections to National funding agencies

5

1 Introduction

The aim of this document is to summarize connections between ACTRIS HO and National Consortia through National Contact points (NCPs). Through the NCPs, ACTRIS Head Office (HO) is connected to national funding agencies, ministries and Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) in Europe.

2 National Consortia and respective National Contact Points

The communication from ACTRIS ERIC towards the national funding agencies is channeled through national ACTRIS consortia and National Contact points (NCP).

In more detail, the national ACTRIS community consists of National Facility Principal Investigators, technicians, engineers, researchers etc. and a national ACTRIS coordinator who brings the community together, talks to the government and participates in ACTRIS meetings together with his/her colleagues. Each national ACTRIS community should nominate a national ACTRIS contact person (NCP) for the relation with the European ACTRIS. Depending on the national ACTRIS organization, national ACTRIS coordinator and national ACTRIS contact person can be the same or different persons. Interim ACTRIS Head Office and later ACTRIS Head Office communicates via national ACTRIS contact person. Table 1 lists the ACTRIS National Consortia and National Contact points as of 11.3.2022. The NCPs have regular joint meetings together with the ACTRIS Head Office on topical issues. The roadmap for ACTRIS countries towards ACTRIS ERIC membership is currently being developed.

The connection to key national funding agencies are channeled through NCPs in their respective contact points listed in Table 1. This is an extraction of information as of 10.3.2022. The updated list as a living document is maintained by the ACTRIS HO.

Within WP 3 we will embark on the discussion with a selected group of national stakeholders to elaborate on the obstacles and opportunities for supporting TNA. At the same time, we will be able to develop access modalities from the perspective of the national stakeholders.

The results of this interaction will be disseminated in the NCP meetings to all National Consortia.

Table 1. Summary of ACTRIS national consortia and National Contact Points (as of 10.3. 2022)

Country	National Consortia (NC)	National Contact Point (NCP)
Austria	ACTRIS-AT	Jochen Wagner
Belgium	ACTRIS-BE	Martine De Maziere
Bulgaria	ACTRIS-BU	Nina Nikolova Dimitar Tonev

Cyprus	ACTRIS-CY	Jean Sciare
Czech Republic	ACTRIS-CZ	Milan Vana
Denmark	ACTRIS-DK	Henrik Skov
Estonia	ACTRIS-EE	Steffen Noe
Finland	ACTRIS-FI	Tuukka Petäjä
France	ACTRIS-FR	Stephane Sauvage
Germany	ACTRIS-D	Ulla Wandinger
Greece	ACTRIS-GR	Nikolaos Mihalopoulos
Ireland	ACTRIS-IE	John Wenger
Italy	ACTRIS-IT	Lucia Mona
The Netherlands	ACTRIS-NL	Arnoud Apituley
Norway	ACTRIS-NO	Tove Svendby
Poland	ACTRIS-PL	Aleksander Pietruczuk Iwona Stachlewska
Portugal	ACTRIS-PT	Daniele Bortoli
Romania	ACTRIS-RO	Doina Nicolae
Spain	ACTRIS-ES	Adolfo Comeron
Sweden	ACTRIS-SE	Erik Swietlicki
Switzerland	ACTRIS-CH	Martin Gysel Beer Stefan Reimann
United Kingdom	ACTRIS-UK	Geraint Vaughan

3 Connections to National funding agencies

Table 2 summarizes selected target countries involved in the more detailed discussions to support new opportunities to support transnational access. By default, the selection is based on the WP3 supported organizations. In the NCP meeting in spring 2022, few additional interested countries were included in the list. The process is open and inclusive and we are ready to expand the participation, if more national consortia would like to join the discussions. The development is regularly reported in NCP meetings. The next NCP meeting will be organized in November, 2022.

Following General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), we only include the name of the contact person of the National Contact points and funding agency contact points in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The detailed contact information (e-mail and phone number) are available through ACTRIS HO or corresponding NCPs.

Table 2. Selected ACTRIS National Consortia and their contact points for the national funding agencies.

Country	Funding agency	Contact person
Austria	Austrian science fund (FWF)	Reinhard Belocky
Czech Republic		
Finland	Academy of Finland (representing Ministry of Education and Science)	Merja Särkioja
	Ministry of Transport and Communication	Hannele Korhonen
France	Agence nationale de la recherche (ANR)	
Germany	German Research Foundation (DFG) Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)	Represented by DLR Projektträger: Christoph Peschke, Jana Theresa Pech
Italy	Italian Ministry of University and Research	Gianluigi Consoli
The Netherlands	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Alice Dijkstra
Poland	Ministry of science and education (MEIN) CNC NCBR	
Spain		

